

Realization of Access, Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in Inclusive Education: What Are the Missing Gaps in Tanzania?

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Abstract

This paper discusses the provision of inclusive education in Tanzania to persons with disabilities. In doing so, it examines the initiatives taken by the government of Tanzania to ensure that all children, including those with disabilities, have access to education. It traces the Tanzania Government's efforts in the provision of holistic education enshrined in equality and equity through the lens of National Strategies for Inclusive Education and other legislative strategies which advocate for all children to be included and have access to education. Further, the paper discusses on the concepts of inclusion and equity in inclusive education as embraced in the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. Through analysis of literature it is still obvious that children with disabilities in Tanzania still face many difficulties in accessing education equitably, due to a shortage of instructional and learning resources, a shortage of trained teachers with skills in handling cases of students with disabilities; and discrimination. This paper concludes by pointing out areas of achievement and weakness in the provision of inclusive education by the government of Tanzania.

Keywords: *inclusive education, equity, diversity, disability.*

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Introduction

Currently, the concepts of inclusive education, equity and diversity are topical international agenda in the provision of education to all children including those with disabilities. More importantly, the agenda of inclusive and equity and holistic education is anchored in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030. The SDGs target equal access in the provision of education to all children to all levels of education and vocational training to the vulnerable groups including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children in vulnerable situations by 2030 (UN, 2017).

The discussion opens up with an overview about key terms used in this paper, namely; inclusion, inclusive education, equity, diversity and disability. Deeply, the paper

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discusses Tanzania efforts in ensuring inclusive education with equity to children with disabilities. The paper also examines challenges of implementing inclusive education. The conclusion and recommendation suggest the way forward for Tanzania in the provision of education to all children with diverse needs with equity.

Conceptualising: Access, Inclusion, Inclusive Education, Equity, Diversity, Disabilities

The term access in the context of education provision is concerned with opening opportunities and enabling all persons to get education irrespective of disability, gender and ethnic origin. Access to education begins with enrolment and progression in learning process (Falk, MacMurdy, & Darling-Hammond, 1995). Broadly, access to education embraces accessibility of learning materials, teachers and school accommodating diverse needs of all children including those with disabilities.

Equity in education is concerned with creating an educational system which accommodates students of all kinds and nurture their educational potentials accordingly regardless of their background, language, race, economic profile, gender, learning capability, disability or family history (Sen, 2009). Succinctly, equity in education is usually associated with equal access to formal education opportunities and resource (Ismail, 2015). In this sense, access dictates that services provided should be available to everyone who is entitled, in this case, be free from any form of discrimination, irrespective of race, ethnicity, culture.

The concept of diversity is widely used in different settings. Diversity generally embraces acceptance and respect, understanding that every individual is exclusive, and recognizing individual differences. (Vyas, 2021). The concept of diversity considers the size of race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socio-economic status, age, abilities, religious beliefs, politics, or other ideologies. Embracing diversity demands tolerance and promotes acceptance and valuing despite individual differences. Above all, accepting diversity fosters a climate where there is fairness and mutual respect (Shakespeare & Watson, 2002, Vyas, 2021). In inclusive education, diversity provides the basis for accepting disability as part of human variation (Ability Junction, 2011). In inclusive classroom context, teachers have the responsibility to identify and recognize the characteristics of diversity among students responding and addressing challenges regarding curriculum design, teaching-learning practices and processes and learning materials, so that the different learning needs of children are subsequently met (Barton,2003; Vyas, 2021).

Socially, inclusion refers to the state of being equally fully participating in all processes in the society regardless of origin, ethnicity or disability (Lunt & Norwich, 1999). In the context of education, UNESCO perceives inclusion as a process of addressing and responding to the diversity of needs of all learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures and communities, and reducing exclusion within and from education (UNESCO, 2005). Inclusion in the context of education requires wide-ranging provision of learning needs including curriculum and content modification, diversifying teaching approaches to embrace diverse learning needs of children with disabilities in inclusive classroom. Further, inclusion calls for change of attitudes of teachers, parents and community to allow acceptance of learning needs of children with disabilities (UNESCO, 2005).

Hence, inclusion is the processes of increasing the participation of students while reducing their exclusion from the cultures, curricula and communities of local schools. Inclusive practice requires significant changes to be made to the content delivery and organisation of mainstream programmes. This is a whole school endeavour which aims to accommodate the learning needs of all students (Booth & Ainscow, 2011; Kearney, 2009).

Inclusive education refers to the process of integrating children with disability in regular classroom; the focus being valuing and acceptance of differences and rights of all students (Kearney, 2009; Skrtic, 1991). The Tanzania government defines inclusive education as a system of education in which children, youths and adults are enrolled in education while participating in regular education programmes regardless of their diverse backgrounds and abilities while eradicating discrimination (URT, 2004). Correspondingly, the Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations, 2016), provides key aspects for defining inclusive education which include: fundamental right to education, education provision to all children that values wellbeing, dignity, autonomy and contribution; and a continuing process to eliminate barriers to education and promote reform in culture, policy, and practice in schools.

The genesis for inclusive education emanates from UN Universal Declaration for Human Rights of 1948 which stipulates that the provision of quality education to all children is a right which has to be ensured to all people (UN, 2015). Recently, more emphasis on inclusive education has been proclaimed by the UN statement and declarations such as the Jomtien Conference of 1990, Salamanca Statement on Special Needs Education and Framework for Action of 1994; and Dakar Framework for Action of 2000 (UNESCO, 1990, 1994, 2000). The Salamanca Statement, for example, directs that the education system should adapt and accommodate the learning diversity of all children including those with special education needs (SEN) in regular schools as a way for addressing negative attitudes in terms of discrimination and stigmatization (UNESCO, 1994).

With regard to values of inclusive education, The British Psychological Society (2002) emphasises that inclusive education should be based on the aspects of rejecting segregation or exclusion of learners, maximizing the participation of all learners in the schools, making learning more meaningful and relevant for all, rethinking; and restructuring policies, curricula, culture and practices in schools and learning environments so that diverse learning can be met. Hence, inclusive education begins with a recognition that all children have a right to be accessed with quality education in equality and equity in the same educational setting (Cobley, 2018; Florian & Rouse, 2001; UNESCO-IBE, 2016).

There are many benefits accrued from inclusive education. The benefits of inclusive education are measured in terms of the positive outcomes for all children, those with disabilities; the disadvantaged groups such as nomads, street children, and ethnic minorities; and those without disabilities. Expounding more, The European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (EASNIE) (2018) has noted that inclusive education increases social and academic opportunities and wellbeing for all groups of children mentioned above in terms of enrolment in higher education, better employment and life outcomes. Categorically, inclusive education is founded in the pillars of access to free and compulsory quality education, with equity, inclusion and non-discrimination (UNESCO, 2005).

According to URT (2012, p.8) considers persons with disability (PWD) as: "... persons with long term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairment which, in interaction with various barriers, may hinder their full and effective participation in the society on an equal footing with others..." In this context, people with disability include: visual impairment, physical impairment, sensori-neuro impairment, hearing impairment, communication and language disability, just to mention some or a few.

Tanzania Efforts in Ensuring Inclusive Education with Equity

Tanzania has been endeavouring to ensure that all children have access and equity to education. In that regard, Tanzania has ratified all international conventions and statements geared for safeguarding the provision of holistic inclusive education. The Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Education (UNESCO, 1994) directs all governments to provide education including those with special needs: "... those with special needs must have an access to regular schools which should accommodate them with a child centred pedagogy capable of meeting those needs" (Peters 2004, p.5).

According to the Dakar Framework for Action on Education for All- 2000 in which Tanzania ratified that protocol, education is a fundamental human right and a key for sustainable development and peace and stability within among countries (UNESCO, 2000). In the two decades before 1981 there was no clear policy to persons with to disability. Although Arusha Declaration of 1967 clearly stated on equality to all people it was until 1981 in the proclamation of the International Year of Disabled People (IYDP) when the government started to take serious measures (URT, 2004). In a bid to implement EFA goals the government of Tanzania has passed different acts and policies for people with disabilities. The Act No.3 of 1982 (Disabled Persons Care and Maintenance) provides and designates responsibilities of caring for disabled persons to families, relatives, local government, central government and non-government organizations.

The formulation of National Policy on Disability (NPD) in 2004 was a landmark for the Government of Tanzania towards the recognition of the rights of the people with disability. NPD provides guidelines and sets parameters for service delivery to Persons with Disabilities (PwDs). The policy underscores services which are required to be provided to persons with disabilities such as: health, education, early intervention, skills and training, employment, care and maintenance. The policy recognizes different groups of people with disabilities: women, children and older people. The policy emphasises that persons with disabilities should be involved in decision making and in all important activities in the society. Further, the policy affirms the government commitment to provide technical assistance in collaboration with stakeholders and to waive fees for technical aids imported into the country and those manufactured in the country (URT, 2004). In 2008, Tanzania embarked inclusive education in education programmes. The Strategy for Inclusive Education (SIE) 2009 -2017 put plans for implementation of inclusive education to Persons with Disabilities (PWD). The SIE outlined strategic areas of action from existing education sector policies and programmes that needed to be reinforced and consolidated so as to provide access to quality education to all children with an emphasis on children with disabilities (MOEVT, 2009). The SIE set the following objectives to be implemented by 2017 including: all education policies and programmes to embrace inclusive values and

practices, teaching and learning to consider and accommodate to the diverse needs of learners, educational support to be available to all learners, to provide training and building professional capabilities for inclusive education and enhance community ownership and participation in inclusive education (MOEVT, 2009).

In ensuring that rights for persons with disabilities, the government of Tanzania in 2010 passed the Persons with Disability Act 2010 which aimed at putting in operational issues in the Disability Policy of 2004. The act directs that Persons with Disabilities (PwDs) have an access to social services including information, communication, sign language, Braille print and disability friendly environment, principles and realization of the rights of PwDs such as respect for human dignity, equality for opportunity and non-discrimination, the responsibility of the central government to PwDs including protection against discrimination and promoting equality, establishment of National Advisory Committee for PwDs and them, the responsibility of the Local Government in providing assistance to PwDs including guidance and counselling and provision of health care, education, rehabilitation and employment (URT, 2010).

Correspondingly, the National Strategy for Inclusive Education (NSIE), 2018 -2021 committed on the provision of education to all groups of people including those with special needs; children and youth by ensuring access, participation and equity. Likewise, the NSIE directed the acquisition of necessary knowledge and skills to special needs groups to enable them to actively contribute to the country's economic transformation into middle income and industrialised country (URT, 2017).

Recently, the NSIE (2022-2026)) is anchored on five values as the milestone for the provision of holistic education in inclusive education, namely; equity, rights to non-discriminatory education, respect to diversity, access for quality education, and collaboration with education stakeholders (URT, 2021). The NSIE has committed to address the persisting challenges in the provision of education in inclusive setting. Such steps for implementation include: improving education policy legislation framework for the purpose of integrating inclusive education values. The NSIE also envisages to improve education to learners with special educational needs, enhancing not only the participation of learners in education but also to ensure their retention in schools (URT, 2021). The NSIE has also glanced on the higher learning institutions to ensure that quality assurance mechanisms in terms of inclusive education are in place to accommodate learning of students with special needs (URT, 2021). Table 1 (Appendix 1) puts a summary of policies and statements implemented by the government of Tanzania in ensuring a holistic implementation of inclusive education.

Implementation of National Strategies for Inclusive Education (NSIE): 2022-2026

In a bid to implement the current NSIE, 2022-2026 the Government of Tanzania through the Ministry of the President's Office - Regional Administration and Local Government (PO-RALG) which is responsible for education for local government released guidelines for implementation of inclusive education. The Guideline for Implementation of National Strategies for Inclusive Education, (URT,2022) aims at providing directives and guidance to supervisors of inclusive education and implementers of inclusive education in different levels of administration in local government. The guideline clarifies the role of different education stakeholders in implementing inclusive education, namely, the PO-RALG, Regional, Districts and

Ward administration. Further, the Guideline directs accountability of different levels of administration in implementing inclusive education.

Alongside key aims of the Guideline, it focused on three important areas. The first part the guideline identifies obstacles and challenges of effective implementation of inclusive education. The second area the Guideline directs procedures to follow in implementing inclusive education in different levels of authorities, namely, the PO-RALG, Regional, District and Ward levels. Finally, the Guidelines illustrates the role of different education stakeholders in implementing inclusive education. These stakeholders include: local governments, village administration, schools, village governments and parents. The guideline also, among others, clarifies five areas for implementation which are enclosed in NSIE-2022-2026 which are: improvement of the provision of inclusive education environment for persons with special needs, establishment of inclusive culture in schools, strengthening the collaboration of different stakeholders in the provision of inclusive education; and monitoring and evaluation of the provision of inclusive education (URT,2021).

Correspondingly, the President's Office - Regional Administration and Local Government (PO-RALG) issued in 2022, the Guideline for Establishment, Administration of Assessment, Identification and Diagnosis Centres for Children with Special Needs (URT,2022)

The Guideline aims to provide directives to local government officers in district levels on the modalities of establishment and administration of diagnostic centres for children with special needs. The Guideline also directs ways of ensuring the availability of diagnostic instruments. Further, ensuring the centres have enough specialists who can conduct identification, assessment and diagnosis; and provision of intervention to children with special needs.

Realization of Inclusive Education Provision in Tanzania

The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) of 1989 emphasizes on the rights of groups who have historically been marginalized or under achieved in school. In article 28, the CRPD stipulates that every child has the right to access education, emphasising that primary education must be free. Primary education must be available to every child (UN, 2016). Tanzania being a member of the United Nations introduced a fee free education to all children in 2016 in order provide opportunities for all children to access education with equity without barriers of poverty and discrimination. Recent studies indicate the increased enrolment of children in primary and secondary schools (Shukia, 2020). Report from Ministry of Education Science and Technology (MoEST) indicated that out of school only 31.7% of pre-primary school-age children were attending school (MoEST, 2016). Similarly, 2 million primary school-age children and 1.5 million lower secondary school-age children were out of school in Tanzania. The report pointed out that poverty was one of the key reason why many children did not attend school. Hence, Thus, the abolition of fees has made it easier and less costly for school-age children to enrol in school. The policy statement on fee-free basic education stipulated in the Government Circular No. 5 (URT, 2015) established to formalise the government's commitment to providing fee-free basic public education, as stipulated in the Education and Training Policy of 2014 (URT, 2015; Shukia, 2020). The Circular also provided directives to corresponding public bodies to ensure that primary and secondary education is free.

Statistics indicate a gradual increase of children enrolment in primary schools in 2021 as compared to previous years. For example, in 2017, pupils' enrolment was 9,317,791 while in 2021, a total number of 11,196,788 pupils were enrolled, an increase of 16.7%. Figure 1 illustrates this.

Figure 1. Standard I-VII Enrolment in Government and Non-Government Schools, 2017 – 2021

Source: URT- National Basic Education Statistics in Tanzania (BEST)

Figure 2. Trend of Number of Pupils with Disabilities in Government and Non-Government Primary Schools by Sex, 2017-2021

Source: URT- National Basic Education Statistics in Tanzania (BEST)

Similarly, enrolment of children with disabilities in primary schools has slowly increased from 24629 in 2017 up to 26404 in 2021, an increase of 6.7%. The enrolment of learners with disabilities is making progress as demonstrated in Figure 2

With regard to secondary education, recent statistics show that a total of 1565201 students were enrolled in secondary education while in 2021, 2379945 students were enrolled, which is an increase of 34.2%. Figure 3 illustrates this enrolment increase.

Figure 3. Total Enrolment of Students in Government and Non-Government Schools, 2011 – 2021

Source: URT - National Basic Education Statistics in Tanzania (BEST)

With regard to students with disabilities in secondary schools, the government of Tanzania has made efforts to ensure that students with all types of disabilities are enrolled in schools as Table 2 (Appendix 1).

The enrolment of learners with special needs is making progress gradually, though a human capital issue needs to be addressed to cater the basic education needs of the persons with disabilities (Aldersey & Turnbull, 2018; UNESCO, 2019). Generally, basing on the statistics above, significant development has been made in the enrolment of children with disabilities in Tanzania.

Challenges of Inclusive Education Provision in Tanzania to Persons with Disabilities

Globally, although, access to education to persons with disabilities is guaranteed, only few persons with disability receive formal education in inclusive education (UNESCO, 2016). In Tanzania, for example, studies indicate that negative attitudes to both parents and teachers towards access to inclusive education is still a barrier for them to complete school and achieve in education (Welwel & Otieno, 2022; Philip, 2022). For example, the study conducted by Philip (2022) in inclusive secondary schools in Central, Western and Lake zones revealed that some general teachers (teachers not specialised

in special education) indicated surprise when some students with disabilities performed well compared to students without disabilities.

Other barriers for access to inclusive education for persons with disabilities include; overcrowded inclusive classrooms and lack of trained teachers in the area of special education (MoST, 2018; UNICEF, 2021; Philip, 2022). For example, the study conducted by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MoEST), (2018) in selected secondary schools with students with disabilities revealed that apart from the challenges of lack of teaching and learning resources, most teachers lacked necessary pedagogical skills for teaching in inclusive classes, including the classes with students with hearing impairment due to deficit training in special needs education. The findings are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Teachers General Qualifications

Source: URT (2018, p.30).

Figure 4 indicates that mostly teachers in sampled schools with disabilities namely; Njombe, Kazima and Mtwara lacked skills of teaching students with disabilities. This situation led to poor academic performance to students with disabilities.

Conclusion

It is clear that the government of Tanzania has strived to ensure that inclusive education with holistic approach is accessed by all children including those with disabilities. The realization of provision of holistic education and inclusive education has been realized through ratification of the United Nations statements and agreement in terms of putting policies and legislations which guide the provision of education with equity through National Policy on Disabilities-2004, Persons with Disability Act-2010 and recent Strategies for Inclusive Education-2021-2026. The government of Tanzania has expanded schools and increased enrolment in schools; primary and secondary schools as indicated in the discussion.

Recommendations

Despite efforts made by the Government of Tanzania in terms of increased enrolment of children with disabilities in inclusive education, still more is needed to be done to enable accessibility and equity to education is realized. It is recommended that the government to expand classes to reduce overcrowdings of children in inclusive classroom. Similarly, provide public awareness about children with disabilities through

campaigns, media, and trainings in order to reduce stigma and discrimination in inclusive education to society and schools. Furthermore, the government should recruit more teachers specialised in special education in order provide assistance to children with disabilities in inclusive schools.

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Appendix 1

Table 1. Number of Students with Disabilities in Government Schools by Type of Disability, Grade and Sex, 2021

Grade	Blind			Low vision			Deaf			Hard of Hearing			Deaf Blind		
	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
Form 1	84	45	129	365	520	885	193	186	379	132	180	312	0	1	1
Form 2	65	78	143	386	500	886	135	163	298	117	173	290	0	1	1
Form 3	51	39	90	310	457	767	104	111	215	75	146	221	1	1	2
Form 4	57	66	123	275	363	638	121	109	230	72	95	167	1	1	2
Form 5	9	2	11	43	40	83	9	16	25	12	11	23	0	0	0
Form 6	16	2	18	53	68	121	8	14	22	11	9	20	0	1	1
Grand Total	282	232	514	1432	1948	3380	570	599	1169	419	614	1033	2	5	7

Table 2. Number of Students with Disabilities in Government Schools by Type of Disability, Grade and Sex, 2021

Grade	Albino			Physical Impairment			Intellectual Impairment			Autism			Multi Impairment		
	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
Form 1	65	85	150	535	409	944	8	12	20	3	4	7	25	12	37
Form 2	75	74	149	476	380	856	10	7	17	10	4	14	8	5	13
Form 3	67	51	118	395	315	710	6	2	8	12	2	14	8	10	18
Form 4	48	65	113	396	270	666	4	5	9	2	3	5	8	3	11
Form 5	19	11	30	72	22	94	2	0	2	0	0	0	3	2	5
Form 6	14	8	22	41	22	63	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	3	3
Grand Total	288	294	582	1915	1418	3333	30	26	56	28	13	41	52	35	87

